

APPLYING THE METHODS OF SUSTAINABILITY BY DESIGN AND PRODUCTION OF CONTEMPORARY WOMAN' ABAYA MADE BY DENIM

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Abstract

Sustainability is one of the modern trends leading fashion design and various design fields, issues of environmental pollution and the need to find solutions that limit the negative effects of civilization have become a necessary need. Sustainability principles have emerged to develop strategies aimed at reducing the damage of manufacturing processes to the environment. The current research aims to design and implement a sustainable Abaya, and build a positive attitude towards this practice, as the Abaya is the national garment for Omani women. The researchers observed that Omani women have a general tendency towards different industrial fabrics, Accordingly, some sustainability principles were adopted to design and implement a sustainable Abaya made of denim fabric. The study recommends establishing a business incubator to produce sustainable fashion in the Sultanate of Oman, especially the women's Abaya, due to its widespread use among society. The sustainability principles that have been applied through current research are: Using natural materials, not using harmful chemicals, using natural dyes, using the recycling fabrics, quality in production, customized production.

Keywords: Sustainability- Sustainable Abaya- Recycling- Natural Dyes- Denim.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The Reasons Leading To the Study

1- Previous studies recommend increasing research work aimed to reducing pollution which resulting by the synthetic textile industry.

-2 Using denim and natural fabrics contributes to recycling the resources and reducing the waste.

-3 Increasing the awareness of the importance of environment preserving and adopting sustainability approaching in designing processes.

-4 Providing opportunities to apply the innovation methods in designing women' Abaya, using denim and natural fabrics in sustainable new style.

5- Emphasizing the value of beauty in natural fabrics such as denim, cotton and linen, and exploring new

trends of contemporary Abayas, and providing such trends to the local community in Sultanate of Oman and Arabic Gulf community in general.

1.2. Problem Statement

-Experimenting the possibility of using natural, sustainable, and ethical fabrics in contemporary fashion production, the aimed product is an outer Abaya which matches the needs of the Arab girl in university activities.

-Exploring the possibility of developing proposals for the decorative design of the Abaya, based on some sustainable methods, such as using natural dyes and downcycling.

1.3. Objectives

-1 Identify the applications of sustainability in fashion design and industry.

-2 Identify the sustainable fashion from a historical perspective.

-3 Identify the effects resulting by fast fashion.

-4 Identify sustainable fashion materials and the properties.

-5 Identify the principles of sustainability in design.

-6 Conducting some experimental samples to apply various sustainable methods.

-7 Designing and producing an Abaya that adopts the sustainability methods in terms of main construction' fabric and the decorative design.

1.4. Methodology

Experimental Development is the research methodology, based on the experimenting a design of modern, ethical Abaya, made of denim. A descriptive analysis methodology for identifying examples of sustainable fashion made by natural fabrics.

1.5. Terminology

-Sustainability: Approach of how natural systems work, diversify and produce everything the natural environment needs to remain balanced. (Gohel, and others 2023)

-Sustainable Fashion: Sustainable fashion: It is a production approach that is keen to avoid harming people or harming the planet, which enhances the well-being of the people who interact with it, and enhances the environment in which sustainability is developed and used as an entry for design, production and consumption. (Haffet, 2020)

- Slow Fashion: The term means awareness and approach to fashion that carefully takes into account the processes and resources needed to make clothes. She advocates buying better quality clothing that will last longer. (Vito, 2023)

-Timeless design: It is a design that is not affected by changes in fashion trends and remains continuous and present forever while achieving aesthetic and functional value in the design. (Braun, 2022)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Preuit, & Yan, (2017) aimed to explore the impact of educating individuals the environmental benefits of slow fashion on their knowledge, attitudes, and purchase intentions towards slow fashion apparel. The results revealed that subjective knowledge and attitude were positive predictors of the purchase intention towards slow fashion. Smith, (2016) aims to advocate for a dematerialized approach to sustainable fashion design, recommended for conducting more research investigating how dematerialised fashion may be applied in practice, and to identify its impact on consumer behaviour. Brewer, (2019) found that legal reforms and increased support for companies that follow more sustainable fashion production practices are necessary to redirect the fashion industry and consumers away from fast fashion models towards more sustainable sourcing, production, distribution, marketing, and consumption practices. That Companies embrace slow fashion practices should set a model for the future of the global fashion industry. Liu, Baines, and Ku, (2022) found that slow fashion concern in priority four considerations; the quality, design, sustainability, and local heritage, these are alternative to the negative social and environmental impact of fast fashion. The study

explored properties of slow fashion that may enhance garment lifetimes. An online questionnaire had been applied on consumers from China, the results showed that Classic/timeless design, ease of maintenance and ease of matching with other clothes emerged as the three most important properties that motivate consumers' long-term use of fashion.

Abo Eid, and Labib, (2021) aimed to recycle the leftover fabrics to achieve the concept of economic product. The results resulted in obtaining new formulations for children's clothing accessories considering what is compatible with contemporary fashion. Rabie, (2021) aimed to emphasize the importance of sustainable methods in the field of fashion industry and apply some methods for tailoring (blouse - dress - trousers - skirts), the research results revealed the possibility of implementing designs simple, modern, contemporary and using methods that use less tools and machines, which achieves sustainable objectives in clothing manufacturing which exploiting resources and reducing waste while meeting the needs of society.

Recycling abandoned clothes has become an urgent need nowadays for many reasons, including maintaining economic need, through Sarhan, and Alatreby, (2018) study, the researchers recycled abandoned scarves to design and produce children's clothing, and the children's acceptance of the proposed clothing was measured. In Salamah, (2021) the study aimed to Introducing sustainable fashion to students, analysing the negatives results of fast fashion production, measuring the students' ability to modify their behaviour for avoiding wearing fast fashion, determining the purchasing decisions of the students towards fast or slow fashion, and explaining the methods used by students disposing their old clothes.

2.1 Benefits of Conducting the Literature Review

These studies have benefited the current research in several aspects, including:

- It is a strong motivation for the experiment, as some studies provided educational modules for students to introduce the significance of sustainability and following the slow fashion style, which the current study is trying to apply by providing Abaya for the Arab women in a sustainable style.
- Introducing the pros of slow fashion versus the cons of fast fashion.
- Identify some of the experiences of researchers and designers in the field of sustainable fashion, so that what is new and compatible with the culture of Arab women can be presented.

3. THE START OF SUSTAINABLE FASHION

The roots of the sustainable fashion and the slow fashion movement in general go back to the 1960s. The hippie movement played a major role in promoting the idea of sustainability. Hippies were promoting the use of recycled clothing and materials and relying on natural and organic fabrics. In the 1980s a small group of environmentally conscious consumers emerged. This period contributed to highlighting the social and environmental aspects of the fashion industry and pushed towards the development of sustainable fashion. Then the fast fashion emerging began between this time and the first decade of the twenty-first century (Gwilt, 2014). As a result of growing alarms about climate change, people are gradually starting to make deliberate changes in their consumption habits. They became more aware of issues of pollution, social injustice, including worker exploitation and child labour in factories. As concern about environmental impacts grows, companies are beginning to exploit sustainability as an attraction, and leading fashion brands are starting to take steps towards sustainability.

3. IMPACTS RESULTING BY THE FAST FASHION INDUSTRY

Water and river pollution:

The textile industry relies heavily on water resources, as it uses huge amounts of water at all stages of its production, from washing fibers to bleaching, dyeing, and washing finished products (Mukherjee, 2015). On average, producing one kilogram of textile requires about 200 liters of water. Many textile mills dump untreated chemicals into rivers and are responsible for some of the most polluted rivers in the world. (Boggon, 2019) (Fig.1-2)

Synthetic dyes:

The dyeing process involves the use of a variety of harmful chemicals, which are usually classified as carcinogens and may affect hormones. In addition to harmful heavy metals such as chromium, copper, and zinc, in addition the dyeing process involves the use of solvents, high temperatures, and heavy metal

catalysts (Mukherjee, 2015).

Air pollution:

Most textile mill operations release emissions into the atmosphere, these gaseous emissions are the largest source of environmental pollution in the textile industry after the problem of liquid waste.

Social impacts:

Due to the labour market needs of the fashion industry, the participation of women and children in the labour has been increasingly promoted regardless of the source of labour, as many women and children migrate from remote and poor agricultural areas to factories located in cities. This type of global trade can contribute to improving the economic level of poor families in developing countries, but there are problems related to low wages, seasonality of work, and the worker during the peak period of export demand may reach 36 continuous hours of work, and they often work in Unsanitary conditions. (Fig. 3-4)

Economic impact:

Economic competition between producers, considering multiple production costs, which include raw materials, energy, transportation, and wages, compel producers and retailers to reduce prices to attract consumers, thus following unsustainable patterns of production. (Bailey, and others 2022)

Sustainable plant fabrics:

Organic cotton:

Organic cotton is high-quality cotton, grown in 100% natural ways and does not affect the environment. It consumes the least water and has the fewest processes in the manufacturing process. Farmers use beneficial insects to suppress harmful insects and use natural plant and animal fertilizers.

Growing organic cotton is more difficult compared to non-organic cotton, but it brings many benefits, as it enhances the community's healthy ecosystem, renews, and maintains soil fertility, improves food security, improves income for the population, reduces the health effects resulting from the use of pesticides and chemicals, and reduces waste, during production and manufacturing.

Organic denim is produced from organic cotton that relies primarily on rainwater irrigation, which means less irrigation, requires 91% less water, 62% less energy, and produces 46% less carbon dioxide than regular cotton. (Ourver, n.d.)

Fig. (1): Fishermen walk on wasted fabric. Fig. (2) The suffering of the people of Bangladesh due to the impact of industrial dyes along the Buriganga River.

Fig.(1) From: <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/features/2022-11-02/h-m-zara-fast-fashion-waste-leaves-environmental-impact>

Fig. (2) From: <https://www.vogue.in/fashion/content/sustainable-fashion-fabric-dye-pollution-ways-to-counted>

Fig. (3): Working children in textile factories. Fig. (4): A found piece of paper that said, "Help me" with one of the clothes.

Fig. (3): <https://fashionindustryforward.wordpress.com/2015/10/11/10/>

Fig. (4) From: https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=IAArHSnLJ_U

4. SUSTAINABILITY PRINCIPLES

- 1- Shifting from quantity to quality: It focuses on making production and consumption depend on quality rather than quantity. This means discouraging continuous growth or accumulation.
- 2- Environmental industry: Encouraging industry processes that reduce waste and respect the environment by preventing the use of harmful chemicals.
- 3- Decent employment: Promoting the provision of living wages for workers and ensuring healthy and safe working conditions.
- 4 - Production on demand: Producing clothing in small batches or according to prior order to avoid storing large unsold quantities.
- 5 -Local supply chain: Enhance the smoothness of the supply chain as local materials are used and local workers are employed to the greatest extent possible.
- 6 -Transparency and Honesty: Focus on transparency and honesty in the supply chain and practices.
- 7- Wash clothes properly: Choose a cold temperature for washing, and do not wash clothes after wearing them once, and use environmentally friendly washing powder. (True, n.d.) (ClimateSeed, 2022)

5. RECYCLING, UP-CYCLING, AND DOWN-CYCLING IN FASHION

Recycling means to keep the product on the same level; however, Upcycling means to raise the quality and downcycling means lowering the quality. In fashion if the consumer re-uses the same garment with some modifications, this equals Recycling, if the consumer used the old, damaged product in a new other design, even this design does not belong to clothing, then this is Recycling. Finally, downcycling involves the process of recycling by utilizing the old fashion parts as a raw material for other lower products.

Denim is one of the materials on which all processes can be performed in the fashion industry, especially recycling, due to its durability and tensile strength.

6. EXPERIMENTAL FRAMEWORK

- Exploratory design :The design was participated in the innovative pavilion at the International Exhibition of the University of Nizwa 22nd 2023. (Fig. 5-8)

The silhouette is achieved and highlighted by the beauty of natural dyes such as saffron yellow from saffron extract, pink rose from beetroot and hibiscus extract and reddish orange. Abundant, easy-to-dye textiles such as natural white recycled cotton and textured denim are used, enhancing the contrast.

Used white cotton was cut into longitudinal strips, and then dyed with natural dyes; the dye was fixed and left to dry. The strips were stretched on a wooden loom and woven in the plain weaving style (1/1 warp and weft).

Some shapes of the dyed material were also cut in the shape of a lotus flower because of the positive meanings it carries, representing (birth) and (ascension), to be installed on the recycled denim skirt.

Fig. (5)

Fig. (6)

Fig. (7)

Fig. (8)

Fig. (5-8): Exploratory design for using natural dyes and recycling old clothes. Displaying the Innovations Paviloin at the University of Nizwa' International Exhibition 2023. The experiment by the researcher/ Al Anburi.

-The first design

The researcher/designer believes that luxury designs play a key role in striking a balance between elegance and preserving our planet. The design is inspired by Monette.

Initially, some experiments were made on free fabrics, and work began in parallel by drawing preliminary sketches, these sketches focused on balancing aesthetics and sustainability in the design of abayas, considering details such as cutting methods and embellishments that could be included to enhance the sustainable and unique look. The details of the waves appear clearly, with the use of colors harmoniously embodying the spirit of impressionist art. The design features delicate details of water lilies, as it appears as if the painting is moving on the magic of the fabric from top to bottom. (Fig. 9-10)

Fig. (9)

Fig. (10)

Fig. (9-10): The first design. Front and side look of a women's abaya design inspired by a Monet painting. The design by the researcher/ Al Anburi.

-The second design

The abaya is creatively designed, as the beauty of denim intersects with the softness of natural fabrics. The white linen fabric adds a touch of elegance, and the blue, white and orange stripes on the shoulders create a bold and fun effect. The lily roses on the right side add a unique and beautiful touch, making this design unique in each detail.

Using the appliqué style by adding natural linen fabric on the right side, which increases the elegance of the abaya, creating a beautiful contrast between jeans and soft fabrics. These details make the design richer with distinctive details. (Fig. 15-16)

Fig. (11): The second design: Designing a women's abaya made of jeans, inspired by lily flowers. The design by the researcher/ Al Anburi.

Fig. (12)

Fig. (13)

Fig. (14)

Fig.(11-14) Trying to implement the design in more than one way, first with leftover cotton fabric for flower units, then forming flowers using sewing threads method.

-Third Design (The Implemented Design)

The researcher/ designer was influenced by the colours of flowers and their natural beauty, which gave the abaya design an artistic and feminine touch, as she was inspired by their colours and shapes to give the design an aesthetic look, thanks to this careful thinking and innovation, the designer has succeeded in

creating a unique abaya that combines modern elegance with everyday comfort. (Fig. 15-16)

In the process of colouring the sketch design, the designer relied on shades of blue and brown to represent jeans and natural fabrics, natural rose colours such as apple red, yellow, olive green and white. The most prominent touches of these colours appear in the flowers that were an essential part of her design.

Fig. (15): The third design, the research produced design. Fig. (16): Distribute flower shapes on the front. The design by the researcher/ Al Anburi.

Later, the pattern was drawn according to the personal measurements of the researcher/designer, Nour Al-Anbarwiyah, and decorative units of natural flowers were distributed on the abaya to create rhythm and graceful balance. (Fig. 17- 21) The longitudinal direction of the fabric was considered when placing the entire pattern parts on the fabric. (Fig.22-23) Several methods have been tried on how to draw straight lines, if they save time and effort and are neat and straight, finally It was printed through the roll, different beige and brown tones have been experimented on the dark blue denim (Fig.24-26)

Fig. (17): The design moodboard.

Fig. (18): The selected flowers' expression.

Fig. (19): Abaya pattern' parts. Fig. (20-21) Preparing the drawing of flowers on the front of the pattern.

Fig. (22-23): Cutting and marking process.

Fig. (24)

Fig. (25)

Fig. (26)

Fig. (24-26): Extracting multiple colour tones to choose the most appropriate - applying the white base to dark blue jeans.

Some techniques have been applied for completing the design, mechanical sewing for attaching the sides and shoulders, hand embroidery for forming yellow flowers, and fabric downcycling for forming pink flowers. (Fig. 27- 30)

At this point white has been chosen as an appropriate base before colouring with brown tones, using the print wheel. The lines were inspired by the beauty of nature and its trees, so I drew vertical and diagonal longitudinal lines on the front and back of the pattern and the sleeves. These lines are not just details, but rather an expression of the shadows of the trees, which added a unique and rich artistic touch to the design, reflecting the beauty of nature in an attractive manner. (Fig.31) After the white colour dried, the scene was coloured with vibrant colours, with brown to complement the splendour of the shadows, with touches of light yellow added for additional brightness. These colour gradations create an enchanting effect, where the colours blend harmoniously, reflecting the splendour of nature and the complexity of its beauty in the fashion design. (Fig. 32-34)

Fig. (27)

Fig. (28)

Fig. (29)

Fig. (30)

Fig. (27-30): The production process.

To add a unique touch, the wild "Anisosciadium" plant has been elegantly embroidered at the bottom of the abaya, a distinct style, where arts and nature meet in an integrated design that carries with it incomparable beauty. The pale-yellow fabric has been transformed into a creative masterpiece of design, recycled with the utmost care, and crafted into innovative and attractive "Forsythia". The designer made this bright colour shine in a new and refreshing way on the abaya, and she also elegantly used the burning technique to clean the edges of the fabric, adding an elegant and unique finishing touch to a fresh look. Old chiffon fabric has been transformed into a unique shape. Using the manipulation technique, the fabrics were skilfully arranged to form charming "Peony" flowers on the abaya, where the purple colour shone with extreme elegance.

After completing the colouring, embroidery, and stitching the fabric, the sides and shoulders were sewn, the sizing was fitted, the sleeves, tail, and top were folded and ironed to make it ready to wear on special occasions. The abaya suits the age of the university student, adds an atmosphere of optimism and is more suitable for wearing in the summer and spring. The project was promoted to become a business incubator at the Entrepreneurship Centre at the University of Nizwa - Fall 23/ 2024.

Fig. (31)

Fig. (32)

Fig. (33)

Fig. (34)

Fig. (31-34): The production process: Printing- painting- embroidering and fixing the 3d recycled fabric' flowers.

Fig. (35)

Fig. (36)

Fig. (35-36) Participation with a poster about the project on the First Research Day at the University of Nizwa, December 14, 2023.

7. RESULTS

The project was approved as one of the business incubators at the Entrepreneurship Centre at the University of Nizwa, the project is keen on:

- Providing a new line of producing sustainable encourages consumers to adopt sustainable clothing and support an environmentally friendly lifestyle.
- The proposed project enhances the concept of social responsibility and ethics in the clothing industry.

- The experiment was not merely an achievement of the research objectives, but rather an embodiment of the spirit of creativity and uniqueness; these sustainable abayas are not just fashion pieces, but rather artistic paintings that reflect purposeful innovation in the world of fashion.

- A positive impact on society can be achieved. Encouraging consumers to adopt a more sustainable lifestyle and highlighting the importance of integrating art and sustainability into the heart of the industry.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Motivating the researchers and designers towards more innovation in the field of sustainable clothing design.

- The youth is one of the society' categories that loves to appear elegant, and at the same time has the motivation for experimentation, innovation, and adopting societal causes. Fashion designers can participate with youth in developing many proposals for sustainability, including, for example, what is known as reversible fashion - modular fashion - zero-waste fashion and others, many innovative approaches.

- Spreading awareness of the positives and necessity of a sustainable trend in consumption, especially in Arab societies in general and in Omani society.

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